

STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT

BY

OBULA CHRISTIAN EBUKA

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Strategic management is an important discipline in business that focuses on setting goals, analyzing competitive environments, and executing plans to achieve organizational objectives. It is the systematic planning, analysis, and execution of actions by developing and implementing plans that enable an organization to achieve its long-term goals and objectives. Strategic management provides organizations with a competitive edge by aligning resources and actions with the dynamic business environment.

This process can include formulating strategy, planning organizational structure and resource allocation, leading change initiatives, and controlling processes and resources. Strategic management involves the formulation and implementation of the major goals and initiatives taken by an organization's managers on behalf of stakeholders, based on consideration of resources and an assessment of the internal and external environments in which the organization operates. Strategic management provides overall direction to an enterprise and involves specifying the organization's objectives, developing policies and plans to achieve those objectives, and then allocating resources to implement the plans.

Strategic management involves analyzing the internal and external environment to identify opportunities, threats, strengths, and weaknesses.

The strategic management process is iterative and dynamic, involving analysis, formulation, implementation, and evaluation.

The strategic-management process consists of three stages: strategy formulation, strategy implementation, and strategy evaluation.

Strategy formulation includes developing a vision and mission, identifying an organization's external opportunities and threats, determining internal strengths and weaknesses, establishing long-term objectives, generating alternative strategies, and choosing particular strategies to pursue. It involves developing strategies based on insights from the analysis.

Strategy-formulation issues include deciding what new businesses to enter, what businesses to abandon, how to allocate resources, whether to expand operations or diversify, whether to enter

international markets, whether to merge or form a joint venture, and how to avoid a hostile takeover.

Strategy implementation means putting formulated strategies into action through resource allocation, organizational structure, and management practices. It requires a firm to establish annual objectives, devise policies, motivate employees, and allocate resources so that formulated strategies can be executed. Strategy implementation includes developing a strategy-supportive culture, creating an effective organizational structure, redirecting marketing efforts, preparing budgets, developing and utilizing information systems, and linking employee compensation to organizational performance.

Strategy Evaluation involves continuous monitoring through Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) ensures alignment with objectives. Strategy evaluation is the final stage in strategic management. In an organization, managers desperately need to know when particular strategies are not working well. Strategy evaluation is the primary means for obtaining this information. All strategies are subject to future modification because external and internal factors are constantly changing. The fundamental strategy evaluation activities comprise of reviewing external and internal factors that are the bases for current strategies, measuring performance, and taking corrective actions.

Tools and Frameworks for Strategic Analysis

Strategic tools provide structured methods for evaluating environments and formulating strategies.

a. Strength, Weakness, Opportunity, Threat (SWOT) Analysis:

SWOT Analysis is a foundational tool used in strategic management to evaluate an organization's internal strengths and weaknesses and external opportunities and threats. It provides a structured framework for identifying factors that influence strategic decision-making. SWOT analysis helps in Strategic Planning, Decision-Making, Risk Management, and Competitive Analysis

b. Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental, and Legal (PESTEL)

Analysis:

PESTEL analysis is a strategic framework used to analyze external macro-environmental factors that impact an organization. It breaks down macro-environmental factors influencing an organization. The acronym stands for Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental, and Legal factors. Understanding these dimensions enables organizations to anticipate opportunities and threats in their environment, making PESTEL a vital tool in strategic management.

c. Porter's Five Forces:

This helps assess industry competitiveness. Porter's Five Forces is a framework developed by Michael E. Porter to analyze the competitive forces shaping an industry and its profitability. It provides insights into the dynamics of competition, helping organizations formulate strategies to gain a competitive edge. The forces are:

Threat of New Entrants

- Bargaining Power of Suppliers
- Bargaining Power of Buyers
- Threat of Substitutes
- Industry Rivalry

The importance of strategic management cannot be overemphasized as it drives success through

- Enhanced Decision-Making
- Helps businesses identify trends, seize opportunities and leverage their unique strengths.
- Optimizes resource allocation efficiently to high-priority activities.
- Prepares organizations for market volatility.

The following are strategic management challenges

- Organizations face pressure to adopt emerging technologies.
- Navigating complex international markets with cultural, legal, and economic complexities.
- Employees often resist strategic shifts due to uncertainty.
- Managing unpredictable external factors like economic downturns or political instability.

In conclusion, strategic management is essential for organizations to navigate complex and competitive environments. It enables long-term success by aligning vision, goals, and actions with changes in the market environment. As the business landscape evolves, organizations must embrace innovation, sustainability, and agility to secure a competitive edge.